

Comparing Tusculum and Arles busts in 3D

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The Tusculum bust is a marble head found in Tuscolo by Luciano Bonaparte. This bust passed to the House of Savoy, with some others items of Bonaparte's collection, and was taken to the Castle of Agliè. About 1940, archaeologist Maurizio Borda, comparing the profile with coins of Caesar, recognized Julius Caesar as portrayed in it. Today, the Tusculum bust is at the Archaeological Museum of Torino. The Arles bust is a marble bust that was discovered in September–October 2007 in the Rhone River near Arles, southern France, by the divers from the French Department of Subaquatic Archaeological Research.

The Arles bust has been studied as a possible portrait of Julius Caesar by many scholars. For this reason it is often compared to the Tusculum bust. Francesco Carotta, in his article https://www.carotta.de/subseite/texte/articula/Sulla_postura_del_Cesare_Tuscolo.pdf, tells that a best manner exists to appreciate the Tusculum bust (that shown on the right of the Figure 1). As a consequence, let us see the Arles bust in the same manner too (Figure 1).

Figure 1: On the right, the Tusculum bust seen as shown by Francesco Carotta, in

https://www.carotta.de/subseite/texte/articula/Sulla_postura_del_Cesare_Tuscolo.pdf On the left the Arles bust, rendered in 3D. (Images courtesy: Francesco Carotta and Wikipedia)

To do this, we can use software developed by Jackson, Bulat, Argyriou and Tzimiropoulos, Nottingham and Kingston Universities. This software is providing a 3D image from a single 2D picture (free demo at <http://www.cs.nott.ac.uk/~psxasj/3dme/index.php>). This approach can give some remarkable hits for any further study based on 3D scans of the busts.